

Bridging Private and Public Blockchains: A zk-SNARK Framework for Secure ERC-1155 Transfers

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Abstract. This study evaluates the current state of blockchain interoperability by analyzing existing cross-chain solutions and their effectiveness in securely transferring digital assets across different blockchain networks. The primary objective is to identify technologies that enable secure and efficient cross-chain transfers, with a focus on the ERC-1155 standard. Through an in-depth analysis, the paper highlights key challenges in interoperability between private-to-public and private-to-private blockchains. Additionally, advanced cryptographic techniques, particularly Zero-Knowledge Proofs are examined for their role in enhancing privacy, security, and transaction validation. As part of this research, a custom relay was developed, successfully bridging token transfers between private and public blockchains using zk-SNARKs. This implementation shows the feasibility of secure, privacy-preserving cross-chain transactions, contributing to the ongoing development of interoperability standards in private-to-public networks.

Keywords: Blockchain, Interoperability, Cross-Chain Bridge, zk-SNARK.

1 Introduction

The blockchain ecosystem remains highly fragmented, with numerous independent networks operating in isolation. Blockchain networks are divided into public and private ones, with different characteristics in terms of accessibility, transparency, privacy and control [1]. While the separation between public and private blockchains is not inherently problematic, it can hinder seamless asset transfers across different ecosystems. This limits blockchain adoption in enterprise and institutional applications that require cross-chain functionality, such as supply chain, digital identity, and financial services.

Currently, there is a strong emphasis on cross-chain communications with focus on public-to-public blockchains networks [2], in sectors like DeFi and cryptocurrencies, to enable the transfer of digital assets between different blockchains. This is key to scaling decentralized asset systems, enabling fast, cross-chain exchange of financial and real-world value beyond a single ecosystem.

However, there is also a growing need for interoperability in private-to-private and hybrid blockchain networks. These settings differ significantly from public networks in terms of consensus mechanisms, permission models, scalability, and monitoring requirements [3], making public interoperability solutions often unsuitable. Without

standardization, enterprises face challenges in integrating multiple platforms securely and efficiently, leading to fragmented systems. While ad hoc approaches may serve specific use cases, baseline interoperability standards would support broader compatibility and security.

Some frameworks, such as Hyperledger Besu [4], offer Ethereum-compatible solutions for permissioned blockchain networks, but interoperability with public blockchains is still in early development. Hyperledger Cacti [5] has provided interoperability solutions focused primarily on private-to-private blockchain connections, but should leverage recent advances in cryptography, such as Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP), to enhance integrity, and confidentiality in cross-chain interactions. The absence of standardized solutions limits the ability of enterprises to leverage both private and public blockchains efficiently, leading to fragmentation and security concerns.

This paper aims to contribute to the practical application and extension of established interoperability patterns, such as Hashed Timelock Contracts (HTLCs), addressing the challenges and proposing an approach that ensures security, privacy, and efficiency in cross-chain private-to-public transactions, and vice versa. Specifically, it evaluates ZKPs as a mechanism to enhance privacy and data integrity in hybrid blockchain transfers. While ZKPs have been proposed in other cross-chain contexts, our approach integrates HTLC-based locking, lightweight encryption, and relayer-assisted proof coordination to enable secure transfers between permissioned and public Ethereum-compatible networks. This proposal is validated within MINE.IO project [6], where a blockchain-based traceability platform has been implemented to manage mining waste using the ERC-1155 [7] standard. This standard allows for efficient token management, supporting the transfer of both fungible tokens, which are interchangeable within the same network, and non-fungible tokens, which are unique and distinguishable. However, achieving seamless interoperability between private and public networks still faces technical and organizational challenges that hinder broader adoption.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 overviews the key technologies for the private-to-public cross-chain transfers. Section 3 presents the design and implementation of the proposed cross-chain mechanism. Section 4 describes some experiments carried out for its validation within the mining waste ecosystem from MINE.IO. Lastly, Section 5 draws the main conclusions and future work of the research.

2 State of Art

Blockchain is a distributed digital ledger technology where data is stored across a decentralized network of nodes, each maintaining a replicate copy of the information. This information is validated by a consensus protocol, ensuring the network reaches an agreement on the state of the ledger. Each piece of data, or transaction, is grouped into a block which is linked to previous ones in a chain using cryptographic techniques, ensuring the integrity and security of the data. Transactions are digitally signed by their creators, making the originator identifiable, and removing the need for central authorities. Consequently, blockchain technology inherently enhances decentralization, transparency, and trust [8].

There are two main types of blockchain networks [9]. The first are public networks, such as Bitcoin and Ethereum, where participation is open to anyone. The second are private networks, which have gained prominence in sectors requiring restricted access, as a governing entity oversees the entry of new participants and determines their permissions. Hyperledger Fabric [10] is a popular option, alongside Quorum, which enhances Ethereum with privacy features for financial use cases, and cross-chain platforms like Polkadot and Cosmos, designed to enable interoperability across independent blockchains. Besu, in particular, supports both public and private networks and allows integration with web3 libraries [11, 12]. Since Besu is based on Ethereum, there is a growing interest in establishing connections with other Ethereum clients. This is particularly important for enterprise solutions that require both the privacy of a permissioned network and the transparency of a public blockchain.

Despite advances in blockchain interoperability, there is still no standardized method to connect Besu with other public Ethereum-compatible networks [13]. The fundamental incompatibilities between private and public blockchains models of governance, consensus, security, and privacy requirements make cross-chain interactions complex.

2.1 Current Interoperability Solutions

Most current interoperability solutions, such as bridges, atomic swaps, relay chains, and sidechains [14] facilitate token swaps and cross-chain communication within blockchain ecosystems.

Private-to-public interoperability remains largely unexplored due to lack of standardization, significant security risks and weak financial incentives. Due to inconsistencies in architecture, asset management, and smart contract logic, achieving seamless interoperability between private and public blockchains remains an unresolved challenge [15]. In addition, some frameworks have already emerged, such as Hyperledger Cacti that facilitates interoperability, but it is not fully decentralized due to the reliance on a node server. Fig. 1 shows a schema that represents how the existing Hyperledger Besu (B1) could interoperate with Fabric (B2) using Cacti in a private-to-private way to transfer an ERC-20 asset, locking it in Besu and minting a key-value asset in Fabric.

Fig. 1. Interoperability between Besu and Fabric using Hyperledger Cacti.

If a token were natively issued on a public EVM-compatible blockchain, interoperability options would be more abundant. Existing cross-chain bridges like Wormhole [16], Axelar [17], and others could facilitate transfers from EVM networks to ecosystems like Solana [18], as illustrated in Fig.2, where an ERC-20 was locked on an EVM chain and a matching SPL token minted on Solana.

Fig. 2. Cross-chain token transfer using Wormhole between Ethereum/Polygon and Solana.

2.2 Key Cross-Chain Mechanisms

Cross-chain interoperability typically requires external protocols, smart contracts, or third-party infrastructure to coordinate asset movements and message passing between networks. There are several mechanisms in the literature that could be considered for cross-chain mechanisms.

- Bridges [19] are one of the most widely used cross-chain solution today. Typically, a bridge relies on a verifier to validate messages from a smart contract on Blockchain A (origin) and relay them to Blockchain B (target).
- Atomic swaps [20] allow direct peer-to-peer exchanges of tokens across blockchains without trust in intermediaries. These swaps occur either simultaneously or not at all, eliminating counterparty risks.
- HTLCs [21] are a type of smart contract that enforces conditional transactions using cryptographic hash functions. Funds remain locked until all participants meet the predefined conditions within a specified period, enhancing security.
- Relay chains [22] act as intermediaries, monitoring multiple blockchains and validating cross-chain transactions. These solutions help to maintain data integrity and prevent fraud while enabling interoperability.
- Sidechains [23] are independent blockchains connected to a primary blockchain. They allow asset transfers between chains while reducing congestion on the main network.

These mechanisms are mainly found in public blockchains due to their need for decentralized, trustless interaction, while private blockchains often rely on direct API integration or middleware instead [24].

Among them, bridges and relay chains often involve third parties or specific ecosystems, making them less suited for hybrid contexts. Atomic swaps are simple but limited in flexibility. Sidechains require complex infrastructure. HTLCs, in contrast, offer a trustless and lightweight solution compatible with both public and private Ethereum-based networks. This makes HTLCs suitable for our mechanism in Section 3.

3 Implementation of Cross-Chain Transfer Mechanism

This section presents an HTLC cross-chain transfer mechanism for Besu and other Ethereum-based public blockchain networks. It is based on three smart contracts and a relay. This mechanism uses on-chain encryption to preserve the inherent decentralization of the blockchain and is also supported by ZKPs to enhance privacy. The objective is to share ERC-1155 between the private and public blockchains. While the explanation emphasizes private-to-public transfers, the mechanism has been tested in both directions, from public-to-private and from private-to-public, ensuring its applicability across different interoperability scenarios.

3.1 Process Overview

The cross-chain transfer mechanism between Besu and an Ethereum-based public blockchain is based on the following operations:

Locking on Besu. A smart contract called Private Bridge (SC1) emits an event when an ERC-1155 token is locked. The Private Bridge is initialized with an ERC-1155 token at the beginning. The lock event contains `encryptedData`, `blockNumber`, `timeStamp`, and `uniqueEventHash`. The `encryptedData` is generated by first formatting the ID and the amount into a fixed-length string (e.g., "0000100005") and then applying a simple XOR encryption using a key derived from the owner's address (`keccak256(owner())`). This lightweight encryption ensures that sensitive lock information is obfuscated but can later be decrypted on the target chain using the same key. The `uniqueEventHash` calculation follows the function $h = H(s, a, t, c)$, where h represents the resulting hash (`uniqueEventHash`), and H is the keccak256 hash function. The inputs include s , which corresponds to the sender's address (`msg.sender`), a , representing the amount (`amount`), t , which is the `timeStamp` (`block.timestamp`), and c , the updated counter. This ensures that each generated hash is unique and derived from these specific parameters, maintaining security and preventing replay attacks.

Event Monitoring & Proof Generation. This setup is a proof-of-concept, where a relay listens for lock events on Besu, generates a Merkle root (a cryptographic hash used to verify the integrity and consistency of a set of data), and creates a ZKP (see Section 3.2). For production, a cloud-based relay would be more scalable and reliable.

Data Transmission to public network. The relay transmits the generated ZKP, the `encryptedData` and the `zkProofHash` to the SC2 (Public Bridge) to verify and mint a new ERC-1155 on the public network.

Verification and Minting on public network. The Public Bridge contains a `mintToken()` method that will interact with a third smart contract SC3, Verifier smart contract, to be deployed on the private network to validate the ZKP received from the relay. ZoKrates, a toolbox for zk-SNARKs on Ethereum, is used to generate and verify this ZKP. See section 3.2 for more details about the ZKP validation. With the private inputs

(*encryptedData*, *blockNumber*, *timeStamp*, *uniqueEventHash*) the ZoKrates circuit recalculates the merkle root. If the calculated merkle root matches with the passed merkle root, the public bridge smart contract finishes its operation extracting from *encryptedData* the amount and id, and creating the equivalent ERC-1155 on the public blockchain.

Fig. 3 shows the private-to-public interoperability mechanism, including the three smart contracts, the relayer, and their main operations. Full implementation in [25].

Fig. 3. Cross-Chain Transfer Flow Using ZKP (EVM-Compatible Private to Public).

3.2 ZK Circuit Implementation and Verifier Smart Contract Generation

Security and privacy-preserving verification of token transfers is achieved through a zero-knowledge circuit implemented using ZoKrates. This circuit specifically validates that the data received by the relayer in the locked event (*encryptedData*, *blockNumber*, *timeStamp*, *uniqueEventHash*) correctly generates the merkle root without publicly exposing these sensitive values. The ZoKrates circuit hashes individual event attributes using SHA-256, concatenates these hashes following a deterministic lexicographical order, and ultimately computes the merkle root.

Once the circuit logic is defined, ZoKrates automatically generates a Solidity verifier smart contract (Verifier). This contract is then deployed to the target public blockchain network. When the bridge smart contract receives a ZKP and the corresponding public inputs from the relayer, it invokes the *verifyTx()* method of Verifier, which recalculates the merkle root following the structured hashing process shown in Fig. 4, to ensure data integrity. First, individual hashes are generated from the *encryptedData* ($h1$), *blockNumber* ($h2$), *timestamp* (hs), and *uniqueEventHash* (hu). These values are then combined into two intermediate hashes: *hashA*, obtained from $h1$ and $h2$, and *hashB*, obtained from hs and hu . Finally, the Merkle Root is computed as $CalculatedMerkleRoot = H(hashA, hashB)$ and compared with the expected *MerkleRoot* to verify its validity. If the proof verification is positive, the bridge contract confirms the authenticity of the event data and securely completes the token minting operation on the public blockchain. This process guarantees that any modification in the input data will result in a different Merkle Root, ensuring the security and consistency of the stored data.

Fig. 4. Merkle Root Calculation Process within the zk-SNARK Verifier Circuit.

4 Evaluation

The proposed cross-chain framework based on ZKP has been applied to the MINE.IO traceability platform which considers ERC-1155 for mining waste pyrometallurgical process traceability. This platform is deployed over a private Hyperledger Besu network to trace the different mining waste assets created, updated and removed during the pyrometallurgical process inside a given mining site. Some details of the pyrometallurgical are considered confidential, such as for instance the obtained refined metals. However, the novel circular economy approaches [26] as well as the strict regulations on the management of mining waste in the European Union [27] highlight the need for the tokens representing waste assets (i.e., tailings, slag, etc.) to be managed in public networks where transparency is greater. For this reason, the mechanism has been considered as an extension of the existing MINE.IO traceability platform for mining waste. Furthermore, integrating tokenized waste into DeFi could unlock new value streams by enabling asset swaps on decentralized exchanges, enhancing liquidity, and generating monetization opportunities such as liquidity incentives and bridge service fees.

4.1 Required technologies

The following technologies have been considered for the validation of the proposed mechanism within the MINE.IO context:

- **Hyperledger Besu**, is a blockchain based traceability platform to trace a pyrometallurgical process of mining waste inside a private mining site.
- **Amoy** [28], a Polygon testnet, enables testing of EVM-compatible smart contracts and cross-chain mechanisms. It simulates interactions between private and public networks, particularly for ERC-1155 transfers.
- **Hardhat** [29] provides the development environment for building and deploying the smart contracts and bridging logic across Besu and Amoy.

- **ZoKrates** [30] enables privacy-preserving, on-chain verification of transactions between Hyperledger Besu and EVM-compatible networks such as Amoy.
- **ZKP**, a technology enabling privacy-preserving verification, has been applied to secure cross-chain interoperability, as in Harmonia [31], and to enable verifiable external calls [32] that validate signed off-chain data on-chain without intermediaries.

4.2 Performance Evaluation of the zk-SNARK-Based Cross-Chain Transfer

Table 1 presents the performance results of the zk-SNARK-enabled cross-chain transfer of an ERC-1155 from Hyperledger Besu to Amoy. The evaluation focuses on key transaction processing stages, including event detection, proof generation, data transmission, verification, and final minting.

Table 1. Cross-chain zk-SNARK Process Results

Process Stage	Time (ms)	Tx Fees (MATIC)
Lock Event (SC1)	5000	0
Proof Generation (Relayer)	38551	0
Verify and Mint (SC2, SC3)	6813	0.015

Lock Event (SC1)

- This step involves locking tokens on the source chain (SC1) to initiate a cross-chain transfer. The smart contract (SC1) registers the lock event, signaling that tokens are reserved and cannot be accessed until verification is completed.
- **Time Taken: 5000 ms (5 seconds).** This duration is mainly influenced by the block time configured in the Besu network (i.e., `blockPeriodSeconds`). In this test, the block time was set to 5 seconds, which aligns with practical settings in permissioned networks. However, this value can be reduced (e.g., to 2 or 1 second) to significantly improve latency.
- **Gas Cost: 0 Ether.** The transaction consumes gas, but no Ether is charged due to the `zeroBaseFee` setting in the Besu genesis configuration.

ZK-Proof Generation (Relayer)

- This stage involves generating a ZKP to prove that the lock event has occurred without revealing sensitive details. The relayer is responsible for computing the proof off-chain before submitting it for verification.
- **Hardware Used:** Intel Core i7, 2 vCPUs, 4 GB RAM. The proof generation time can be reduced with higher specs.
- **Time Taken: 38551 ms (38.6 seconds).** This is the most computationally intensive step, as zk-SNARKs require heavy cryptographic processing. While

this duration may appear long, it is performed off-chain and can be optimized through better hardware or parallel computation.

Verification and Minting (SC2, SC3)

- The ZKP is verified on the destination chain by the Verifier (SC3) using the zk-SNARK verification algorithm. Once validated, the corresponding minting transaction takes place on the PublicBridge smart contract (SC2), releasing the equivalent number of tokens on the target blockchain.
- **Time Taken: 6813 ms (6.81 seconds).** The verification process is relatively fast compared to proof generation, as zk-SNARKs are designed for efficient verification. The minting process adds a small delay.
- **Gas Cost (Tx Fees): 0.015 MATIC .** This is the only step incurring transaction fees, as both zk-SNARK verification and token minting require on-chain execution. The cost remains low thanks to the use of Polygon, a high-throughput and low-fee network. Compared to similar operations on Ethereum, this significantly improves overall efficiency, making the solution more scalable and practical for real-world cross-chain deployments.

These results highlight a balanced trade-off between privacy-preserving guarantees and transaction latency. The 5-second lock delay is adjustable and can be reduced in Besu by tuning the `blockPeriodSeconds` parameter, thus enhancing performance for enterprise or high-throughput applications. The zk-proof generation, while computationally expensive, does not impact the user experience directly and benefits from future hardware and algorithmic optimizations. Lastly, the verification and minting on a low-cost chain like Polygon demonstrate that zk-SNARK-based bridges can be both secure and economically viable at scale. Moreover, the use of ZKPs and encrypted inputs reduces the trust assumptions on the relayer, as it cannot access or alter the proof content, although it still plays a critical role in message delivery and availability.

5 Conclusions and future research

The design and implementation of zk-SNARK-based cross-chain transfers has demonstrated its feasibility for secure and scalable token migration between private (Hyperledger Besu) and public (Amoy) blockchain networks. The system successfully integrates lock event monitoring, proof generation, verification, and ERC-1155 minting, ensuring end-to-end interoperability.

The tool has been integrated in the MINE.IO blockchain based traceability platform for mining waste assets, opening the possibility of extending its use to circularity economy environments in which transparency is a requirement, as well as unlocking monetization opportunities, such as revenue generation for liquidity providers, bridge service fees, and potential financial incentives within the public blockchain ecosystem.

This is a domain-agnostic tool that can be considered for use across different EVM-compatible blockchains, involving already existing assets that require greater transparency or new financial opportunities, while maintaining full history traceability.

Future work may involve enhancing the encryption scheme beyond basic XOR, evaluating alternative ZKP frameworks like Circom [33] to improve proof generation and verification efficiency, and exploring zk-SNARK aggregation or adaptive batching mechanisms to reduce computational and gas costs.

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References

1. Strehle, E.: Public versus private blockchains. BRL Working Paper No. 14, Blockchain Research Lab (2020)
2. Ghosh, B.C. et al.: Leveraging Public-Private Blockchain Interoperability for Closed Consortium Interfacing. In: IEEE INFOCOM 2021 – IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, pp. 1–10. IEEE, Vancouver, Canada (2021)
3. Belchior, R. et al.: A Survey on Blockchain Interoperability: Past, Present, and Future Trends. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 54(8), 168 (2021)
4. Fan, C. et al.: Performance Analysis of Hyperledger Besu in Private Blockchain. In: 2022 IEEE International Conference on Decentralized Applications and Infrastructures (DAPPS), pp. 64–73. IEEE, Newark, USA (2022)
5. Hyperledger Cacti, <https://github.com/hyperledger-cacti/cacti>, last accessed 2025/03/28
6. MINE.IO Project, <https://mineio-horizon.eu/project/>, last accessed 2025/03/28
7. Ethereum Foundation, ERC-1155 Token Standard Documentation. <https://ethereum.org/en/developers/docs/standards/tokens/erc-1155/>, last accessed 2025/03/28
8. Singhal, B. et al.: How Blockchain Works. In: Beginning Blockchain: A Beginner’s Guide to Building Blockchain Solutions, pp. 31–148. Apress, Berkeley (2018)
9. Guegan, D.: Public Blockchain versus Private blockchain. Documents de travail du Centre d’Économie de la Sorbonne 17020, Université Panthéon-Sorbonne (2017)
10. Androulaki, E. et al.: Hyperledger Fabric: A Distributed Operating System for Permissioned Blockchains. In: Proceedings of the Thirteenth EuroSys Conference, pp. 1–15. ACM, Porto, Portugal (2018)
11. Praitheeshan, P. et al.: Private and Trustworthy Distributed Lending Model Using Hyperledger Besu. *SN Comput. Sci.* 2(2), 115 (2021)
12. Shahrukh, M.R.H. et al.: A New Approach to Financial Distribution Systems Leveraging Hyperledger-Besu and Consortium Blockchain. In: 2023 26th International Conference on Computer and Information Technology (ICCIT), pp. 1–6. IEEE, Bangladesh (2023)
13. Ethereum Foundation: Ethereum Developer Documentation. <https://ethereum.org/en/developers/docs/>, last accessed 2025/03/25
14. Wang, G. et al.: Exploring Blockchains Interoperability: A Systematic Survey. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 55(13s), Artículo 246 (2023)
15. Morháč, D. et al.: Unispell: Universal Adapter for Interoperability in Polkadot Paraverse. *ClusterComputing*, 28, Article 311 (2025). <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10586-025-05183-6>

16. Wormhole Documentation, <https://wormhole.com/docs/>, last accessed 2025/03/28
17. Axelar Network, <https://axelar.network>, last accessed 2025/03/28
18. Yakovenko, A.: Solana: A New Architecture for a High-Performance Blockchain v0.8.14. Solana Labs, San Francisco, USA (2018)
19. Zhang, M. et al.: SoK: Security of Cross-chain Bridges: Attack Surfaces, Defenses, and Open Problems. arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.12573 (2023)
20. Han, R. et al.: On the Optionality and Fairness of Atomic Swaps. In: Proceedings of the 1st ACM Conference on Advances in Financial Technologies (AFT'19), pp. 62–75. ACM, Zurich, Switzerland (2019)
21. Monika, B. et al.: Hash time locked contract based asset exchange solution for probabilistic public blockchains. *Cluster Comput.* 25, 4189–4201 (2022)
22. Li, B. et al.: Performance Modeling of Relay Chain. In: IEEE Proceedings, pp. 1–10. IEEE (2025)
23. Purnaadi, C.W. et al.: Sidechain implementation strategies to improve blockchain scalability. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 2920, 020005 (2024)
24. Anglen, J.: Blockchain Interoperability: Bridging Diverse Networks for Seamless Integration. *Rapid Innovation*. <https://www.rapidinnovation.io/post/blockchain-interoperability-bridging-diverse-networks-for-seamless-integration-2024>, last accessed 2025/05/05
25. Valarezo-Castañeda, D.: zk-crosschain-besu-amoy. GitHub repository, <https://github.com/dariusjvc/zk-crosschain-besu-amoy>, last accessed 2025/03/28
26. Kinnunen, P.H-M. et al.: Towards Circular Economy in Mining: Opportunities and Bottlenecks for Tailings Valorization. *J. Clean. Prod.* 228, 153–160 (2019)
27. Hámor, T.: Sustainable Mining in the European Union: The Legislative Aspect. *Environ. Manag.* 33, 252–261 (2004)
28. Polygon Labs: Introducing the Amoy Testnet for Polygon PoS. <https://polygon.technology/blog/introducing-the-amoy-testnet-for-polygon-pos>, last accessed 2025/03/28
29. Hardhat Documentation, <https://hardhat.org/docs>, last accessed 2025/03/28
30. Eberhardt, J. et al.: ZoKrates – Scalable Privacy-Preserving Off-Chain Computations. TU Berlin, Berlin, Germany (2018)
31. Belchior, R. et al.: Harmonia: Securing Cross-Chain Applications Using Zero-Knowledge Proofs. Instituto Superior Técnico INESC-ID, Lisbon, Portugal (2023)
32. Ellul, J. et al.: Active External Calls for Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies: Debunking Cited Inability of Blockchain and DLT to Make External Calls. Centre for DLT, University of Malta, Malta (2023)
33. Bellés-Muñoz, M. et al.: CIRCOM: A Robust and Scalable Language for Building Complex Zero-Knowledge Circuits. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain (2023)